

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGE SKILLS

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

Department of English practical course

The practice of teaching language aspects

Narbekova Ra'no Usmanovna

Annotation: Nowadays, technology is very important part of our life in every sphere. It helps us to make our work easy, fast and effective. In the article importance and advantages of technology in learning language were discussed. Moreover, Useful online learning platforms for foreign language learners were highlighted.

Key words: *online learning platforms, authentic, instructor-designed, learner-centered, ACTFL acknowledges, [language labs](#), authentic interaction, Flexible learning.*

It is not secret that technology is now a part of our everyday lives, and it's hard to remember how we got by without it. In the education sector, technological development has revolutionised the way we teach, making the learning experience truly transformative. Through technology, educators can better meet the learning needs of students, making education more accessible, inclusive and engaging. Technology offers greater flexibility in the way we study. Unlike more traditional ways of learning where students would have to travel to access physical resources at a library, technology has enabled students to access learning resources with the click of a button.

The rise of online learning platforms has produced a wide range of courses and resources that can be accessed anytime and from anywhere, regardless of where you're living in the world. With video conferencing tools, online

collaboration platforms, and virtual classrooms, students can participate in real-time classes, interact with teachers and peers, and submit assignments online. This flexibility is particularly beneficial for students who have other commitments, such as work or family, or cannot attend traditional in-person classes[1]. Technology can and should be used by language educators to enhance language instruction, practice, and assessment, as articulated in the World-Readiness Standards for Learning Languages. Through the purposeful use of technology:

- Students read, listen to, and view authentic, engaging, and timely materials from the target culture.
- Students practice interpersonal skills as they interact via video, audio, or text in real-time with other speakers of the target language.
- Students collaborate on presentational tasks with their peers or teacher, anytime, anywhere.
- Students work at their own pace as they access online content and/or utilize computer adaptive programs managed by their teacher.
- Students practice discrete skills with engaging online games and applications.
- Students benefit from differentiated instruction where multiple applications can be used to assess students, assign varied tasks, track data, give real-time feedback, and manage classrooms and lessons.

The use of technology is not a goal in and of itself; rather technology is one tool that supports language learners as they use the target language in culturally appropriate ways to accomplish authentic tasks. Further, all language learning opportunities whether facilitated through technology or in a classroom setting, should be standards-based, instructor-designed, learner-centered, and aimed at developing proficiency in the target language through interactive, meaningful, and cognitively engaging learning experiences[2]. ACTFL acknowledges a role for hybrid, online and distance learning instructional models aligned with state and

national standards and facilitated by language educators. The development of technology is best driven by the needs of the language learner, supporting the kinds of interactions our students need to become college, career, life, and world-ready.

The use of technology has become an important part of the learning process in and out of classrooms and is viewed as the core requirement in modern schools and universities. Modern language teaching and learning technology includes but is not limited to [language labs](#), online learning platforms, digitalization, multimedia devices, mobile phones, learning apps, flashcards, audio/visual multimedia content (like podcasts and videos), EdTech solutions, and social media which can facilitate faster and more comprehensive language progression. For example, the application of multimedia content in class could integrate print texts, video, learning games, and the internet to familiarize students with language vocabulary and structure or let them practice pronunciation and speaking with native speakers.

1. Wider exposure to the target language and cultural contexts

Technology increases the students' opportunity for authentic interaction with native speakers and other language learners at various levels within or outside the classroom. Practice leads to perfection and technology-rich language learning makes it possible.

2. Higher motivation and attention during the language course

Transforming from passive recipients to active learners, students might feel very excited about language learning and are motivated to practice more, using devices with which they can practice a language through features such as voice recognition and interactive multimedia exercises, etc.

3. Flexible learning

Much more freedom is given to students within the classroom to decide how they approach the language and choose when and where to learn outside the classroom. Self-decision making and individual responsibility-taking stimulate more profound and enriching linguistic immersion.

4. Adaptive learning

Technology has made it possible to create adaptive learning systems that can track a student's progress and adjust lessons accordingly. This helps provide a more tailored learning experience, making it easier for students to learn at their own pace and focus on areas they need improvement in[3].

One of the biggest problems faced when looking for great tools to use is that there are so many out there and it can be hard to know which to choose. For that reason, we've gathered together a list of some of our favourite language learning tools out there.

- Text Inspector- Text Inspector is a professional standard tool that can be used by both student and teacher to assist in the language-learning process.
- Quizlet- [Quizlet](#) is a free learning app that can help EFL students to learn and master vocabulary and grammar. Offering simple flashcards and games, it's a great way to gamify language learning whilst still getting results. EFL teachers can upload their own class materials and share with students or students can create their own sets based on their notes.
- Netflix- For intermediate to advanced English students who want to improve their language comprehension skills in a fun way, [Netflix](#) can be the perfect solution. It offers a range of movies and TV shows from around the planet and there's someone for everyone's taste. You can also add English subtitles to the shows to help with your comprehension and often add subtitles in your native language if you're a newer learner. Shows like 'Stranger Things', 'House of Cards' and 'The Crown' are excellent choices.
- HelloTalk- [HelloTalk](#) is a fantastic free app that helps you connect with native speakers, make new friends and practice your language skills in an informal, low-pressure way. It comes with voice chat, text chat and doodle share features and you can even record a voice message and send to your new friends if you're too self-conscious to have a live conversation.

- Podcasts- Podcasts are an effective way for your students to listen to more spoken English and to improve their comprehension skills for free. They're also very convenient- you can either listen to them on your laptop or download them to your smartphone for on-the-go learning. Some also come with useful transcripts.
- Duolingo- [Duolingo](#) is a language learning tool that can provide useful practice for learners outside of the classroom. It helps to gamify the language-learning process, providing 'rewards' for continued use which can help keep English students of all ages motivated.
- Grammarly- Although [Grammarly](#) is an app aimed at native speakers, it can also help your students improve their written English independently. It highlights typos, spelling mistakes and grammatical errors and makes useful suggestions regarding how to best correct the mistake. It's not always 100% correct so it should be used with caution, but can be a useful learning tool[4].

Summing up all given facts above it should be noted that Technology is having a growing impact on foreign language learning worldwide. The landscape of language teaching and language learning has transformed so rapidly that the formal classroom does not serve as the primary language learning site anymore. Enhancing language learning with e-learning apps and technology is nothing new since our formal education system has used different educational technology tools and multimedia based learning content for already decades. Mohammad Reza Ahmadi (2018) argued that educational technology tools appeal greatly to language instructors due to their contribution to enhancing learner autonomy as well as students' active engagement and maximizing positive language learning outcomes.

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